

What Explains the Post-Quota Gender Gap in National Parliaments? On Gendered Career Opportunities in Multi-Level Austria

Philipp Korom
Institute for Advanced Studies
Josefstädter Strasse 39, 1080 Wien
Mail: philipp.korom@ihs.ac.at

Bio

Philipp Korom is currently the PI of the project “National and political local political elites in Austria” (P31967) that is funded by the Austria Science Fund (FWF), ORCID: 0000-0002-7517-1993

Funding Details

This work was supported by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) under Grant P31967

Disclosure Statement

The author reports there are no competing interests to declare.

Word Count:

7,681

What Explains the Post-Quota Gender Gap in National Parliaments? On Gendered Career Opportunities in Multi-Level Austria

This article examines the persisting gender gap in the Austrian national parliament after the introduction of voluntary gender quotas at the party level ('post-quota gender gap'). The pre-parliamentary careers of 703 members of parliament (*Nationalratsabgeordnete*) were studied using social sequence analysis to understand the career opportunities of men and women running for a legislative mandate. The findings highlight how the gap mostly stems from a gender skew on local career pathways to parliament. The career transitions from local politics to the national parliament are especially male-dominated in parties with bottom-up candidate selection procedures. Overall, the case study highlights a vicious link in a federal state architecture: In Austria, with its nine states and over two thousand cities and municipalities, the gender gap at the local level significantly plays out at the national level.

Keywords: political careers; political elites; federalism; Austrian politics; gender; social sequence analysis

Introduction

Recent years have witnessed a wide range of initiatives to increase the representation of women in parliaments. The European Union, for example, started making statistics publicly available on how far Member States are from achieving a gender-equal society. The average proportion of women candidates in the last few parliamentary elections across the EU have increased mostly due to legislative candidate quotas to 33% in 2022 (EIGE 2022). Equal representation has not yet been achieved and historic data reveals staggering gender imbalances over many decades. In Austria, the country studied in this article, the share of female members of parliaments (MPs) hovered around 5% between the 1950s and 1970s, rose to about 10% in 1979, and passed the 30% mark only after the 2002 parliamentary election (Geisberger 2010).

Women's underrepresentation entails a principal problem for parliamentary democracies for at least three reasons: The absence of female role models in public office, the undermining of equality of opportunity, and the misrepresentation of women's interests (Phillips 1998). First, the low exposure to gender role models is very likely to decrease women's political ambition and interest in running for office, which, in turn, perpetuates the gender gap (Fox and Lawless 2014). Second, a gender gap that stems from discrimination severely hurts the widely held principle that positions of social advantage should be open to all (Rawls 1999). Third, there is growing evidence for the link between 'standing for' and 'acting for' representation (Pitkin 1972). (1972) If there is a critical mass of female legislators, women (as well as men) are especially likely to act on behalf of women (Cowell-Meyers and Langbein 2009; Höhmann 2020).

Although awareness of these harmful effects of women's underrepresentation in parliaments has risen significantly in recent years, the multiple causes of the gender gap are yet not fully understood. Most studies have adopted different variants of the supply and demand model of political recruitment to explain this phenomenon. This theory was advanced by Norris and Lovenduski (1995) and theorises candidate selection as an interactive process in which both selectors (i.e., parties) and aspirants affect outcomes that are organised in several sets of institutions. Supply-side factors affect who comes forward, while demand-side factors affect who is successful at the application, approval, selection, or election stage. While some scholars stress that too few women have high political ambitions due to low levels of motivation and gender role constraints (Fox and Lawless 2004), others find that the diminishing share of women in successive recruitment stages plays a much greater role (Ashe 2020) – a phenomenon often described as 'gendered pipeline' (Thomsen and King 2020). Given the fact that supply-side factors cannot explain why women face barriers once they formally decide to seek candidacy, Ashe and Stewart (2012, 688) have called on moving 'beyond the supply or demand debate' and start focusing on the gatekeepers who discriminate against women.

Taking up this desideratum, this article studies pre-parliamentary career pathways in the Austrian multi-level political system, thereby aiming to detect intraparty practices that can help explain the persistent gender gap. Previous research has established that the careers of legislators can take very different trajectories (e.g., Ohmura et al. 2018) but, in most cases, unfold over longer time periods with

candidates systematically working their way up the party ladder. This article's main contribution is to show that in political federalism's local routes to legislative power—that is, direct career transitions from local politics to national legislative power—are not only a regular occurrence but also a male-dominated phenomenon. I will argue that in Austria, with its nine states and over two thousand cities and municipalities, the gender gap at the highest political level is, at least partly, a reflection of existing gender inequalities at the lowest level.

The article is structured as follows: (1) Introduction of useful general concepts for thinking about 'careers through the party' (Fiers and Secker 2007) and a review of literature on how political parties make or break legislative careers; (2) Presentation of the Austrian case; (3) Compiling of the different pieces of the research puzzle tackled—what causes the post-quota gender gap?; (4) Identification of seven typical career patterns, based on political career data on all members of the Austrian parliament between 1996-2019 (N=703), and evidence for a gender skew towards men on all local career pathways; (5) General conclusions drawn on how the multi-level state architecture can impact women's political careers.

Gendered Careers in Federal Political Systems

Careers can be understood in structural terms as ‘successions of related jobs, arranged in a hierarchy of prestige through which persons move in an ordered (more-or-less predictable) sequence’ (Wilensky 1961, 523). Careers in politics are distinct from those in other industries such as business, as they are accompanied by a higher risk of ending abruptly, especially if political positions are up for electoral grabs. Furthermore, entry into professional politics is far less dependent on formal degrees or certificates. Therefore, career paths are not clearly regulated, which implies that very different careers can lead to the top in politics (Edinger and Jahr 2015).

Career choices are, in general, determined by individual ambitions and structural opportunities. Most politicians aim for higher income, career maintenance, or career advancement. However, as empirical studies show, individual drive and determination becomes collectively structured by institutional settings that determine the availability, accessibility, and attractiveness of job positions. Where in this context availability, accessibility, and attractiveness can be defined as follows (Borchert 2011, 121–23): Availability denotes the sheer number of existing offices (e.g., federalism increases the number of available offices); accessibility describes the relative ease with which a certain position can be obtained (e.g., it makes a difference whether or not there are strong incumbents); attractiveness refers to the properties of the office itself (e.g., jobs with higher income).

How actors navigate their careers in federal systems between the local, regional and national levels of the political system differs, to some extent, between countries as country-specific institutional configurations determine the direction (and speed) of career moves (Stolz 2003). Most careers roughly correspond to one of three idealised career patterns in regionalised and federal systems distinguished by Borchert and Stolz (2011): unidirectional, alternative, and integrated. Unidirectional patterns follow the organisation of the state from the local to regional and national levels. Alternative career paths develop if highly attractive offices have cognitive, legal, or political boundaries between levels of government or types of institutions, and if careers unfold mostly within one single level of government. While integrated career circuits develop if political arenas are not sealed off from each other and multidirectional ‘level-hopping’ becomes the rule rather than the exception.

At the core of this typological thinking are, thus, mobility opportunities that may or may not be equally open to men and women in politics. This is why the sensitising concepts of unidirectional, alternative, and integrated political careers appear useful to organise evidence in gender-sensitive research. So far, it is unclear, whether these three prototypes of pre-parliamentary careers in federal systems tend to be gendered. The scarce gender-sensitive literature on legislative careers found some gender differences with regard to how women and men ‘get in’ and ‘get on’. Overall, women find it difficult to ‘get in’ as party recruiters tend to be men who draw on their male-dominated personal networks in search for candidates (Sanbonmatsu 2006). Gender-homophilous recruitment networks are especially harmful to women’s representation in parliament as women are less likely than men to run if not actively recruited by (local) gatekeepers (Fox and Lawless 2004). Studies looking at career trajectories (‘getting on’) found that similarities in the legislative careers of men and women outnumber the differences (e.g., Schwindt-Bayer 2011). On the other hand, further research concluded that men are more likely to embark on the classical party career than women (e.g., Ohmura et al. 2018). While local and regional pathways to legislative power are well-documented (Turner-Zwinkels and Mills 2020), little is still known about the barriers to women’s advancement in multi-level political systems.

The Austrian Case

Electoral System

The Austrian parliament is composed of an upper house, the *Bundesrat*, whose members are appointed by the legislatures of the states of Austria (*Länder*), and a lower house, the *Nationalrat*, whose 183 members are directly elected every five years (or sooner). The *Nationalrat* is based on what can be called a party-list system of proportional representation. The seats, often referred to as “mandates”, are assigned to the political parties under strict rules, where the key is the percentage share of total votes that they have obtained. Since 1992, elections to the National Council have used a three-tier electoral system with a seat allocation mechanism that connects all three tiers in a bottom-up process. A state-wide electoral quota is used to allocate seats at both the regional constituency and the state level. Seats won by a party at the regional constituency level (39 regional districts), or direct mandates, are subtracted from its corresponding state-wide seat total (9 *Länder*), and the remaining mandates come from the party’s state lists. Finally, all 183 National Council seats are distributed at the federal level by the ‘d’Hondt rule’ (Müller 2005).

Proportional representation is combined with a closed list system: regional, state, and federal lists of candidates are defined by the machine of the party and candidates are elected according to their pre-stated position on these lists. While voters can cast one preferential vote in the regional constituency and another one in the higher-level constituency, there is firm evidence that chances of being elected highly depend on the candidate’s initial position on the lists, as very few candidates have succeeded in gaining sufficient votes to move to the top of the party list based on voters’ preferences (Harfst et al., 2021).

The three-tier electoral system creates different types of candidates, depending on the level(s) at which the candidates run—regional, land, national—and whether multiple candidacies are combined (Müller et al. 2001). Well-placed regional constituency candidates are often as well placed prominently on their party’s Land list but prefer, as a rule, winning a regional constituency seat because these are, in general, more shielded from intra-party competition in re-elections than Land seats (Eder, Jenny, and Müller 2015).

Political Parties and Gender Quotas

In Austria, as there are no legislative quotas in place, voluntary party quotas are *the* ‘fast track’ to equal representation for female candidates. The Social Democratic (Socialist, before 1991) Party (SPÖ) was the first Austrian party to adopt a 25 % women’s quota for candidacies in national elections in 1985, and a gender ‘zipper system’ was added to the party statute in 2010 (Steininger 2000). What is more, in 1985 a 40 percent quota for women on party lists was established.

The Austrian People’s Party (ÖVP), which can be seen as a laggard, followed with the introduction of a women’s quota of 33.3% for all party executive bodies, candidate lists, and MPs. A new party statute introduced in 1995 aimed to achieve a more balanced proportion of women and men in all bodies. To reach this goal, gender zipper lists for the national and the Land district candidate lists were introduced, thereby exempting the regional district lists (Jenny 2018, 39).

While the Greens included already in 1987 a 50% quota in its articles for all elected organs and party functions, the right-wing Austrian Freedom Party (FPÖ) – the third-strongest party in Austria’s parliament – as well as the pro-business and anti-euro party Team Stronach consistently opposed a quota for women. The New Austria (NEOS) party, founded in 2012, allows all citizens to apply for candidacy and the three selectorates, formed of citizens, the party executive and party members, vote online on candidates.

To understand how intra-party rules affected the composition of MPs, Figure 1 depicts the evolution of the gender gap within selected parliamentary parties between 1945 and 2019—a time span that covers eleven legislative episodes. The figure shows that in the decades following World War II the ÖVP and the SPÖ, the two leading and mostly governing parties, each recruited only about ten or fewer women to the *Nationalrat*, which at first had 165 members and then 183 members from 1971 onwards. In total, 84 female MPs and 495 male MPs took their seats for the ÖVP, while 129 female MPs and 450 male MPs filled seats for the SPÖ. With the exception of the Greens and the NEOS, the blatant gender gap grew smaller but remained significant. In the 2013-2017 legislative period, for example, the share of female members of parliament was less than 40 percent in the ÖVP and SPÖ. It can be inferred as well that the share of women was persistently higher in the SPÖ compared to the ÖVP and hovered

around 20% in the case of the right-wing party FPÖ. One can conclude that the introduction of gender quotas did *not* close the gender gap in Austria's three large parties (ÖVP, SPÖ, FPÖ).

Figure 1. Members of the Austrian *Nationalrat* by Gender and Party Affiliation (1945-2019).

Note. The red line indicates the share of women in percentage points.

Research Puzzle

Given the evidence-base detailing that gender quotas and the zipper system are effective in closing the gender gap in national parliaments (EIGE 2022), the persisting underrepresentation of women in Austria's *Nationalrat* presents a research puzzle. Previous research that tackles the post-quota gender gap engages with six standard explanations: (1) poor social acceptance of quotas, (2) male party networks, (3) persisting gender practices in parties, (4) a small candidate pool of women, (5) lack of resources by and for women candidates, (6) problems in reconciling family and work responsibilities (Ahrens et al. 2020, 39).

This study does not aim to comprehensively solve the research puzzle but rather to approach the phenomenon from a new angle, which promises unprecedented insights into the causes of women's underrepresentation in national parliaments. The adopted perspective focuses on career trajectories and gender diversity in the main routes to legislative power. The central assumption made is that if the number of pathways to legislative power is more limited for women than for men, then it is likely that gendered careers patterns contribute to the gender gap in national parliaments.

This article examines barriers that make it likely that women (with the ambition to become legislators) have fewer career options to enter parliament. While the research design does not allow us to disentangle to what extent gendered career patterns are caused by systemic (culture and structure) determinants and/or by women's choices (or an interaction of both), the study of orderly careers does allow us to determine the degree to which women are excluded from unidirectional, alternative, or integrated careers. As "careers through the party" clearly dominate across Europe (Fiers and Secker 2007), the identified gendered trajectories of interconnected political jobs are able to highlight organisational opportunity structures *within* parties that disadvantage women.

The study will proceed in two steps to answer two crucial research questions: First, what are the main pathways to legislative power in Austria? Second, which of these career routes are male-dominated?

Methodology

Data

Career information on all members of the *Nationalrat* between the 20th legislative period (1996-1999) and the 26th legislative period (2017-2019) were gathered using the *Who is Who* edited by the Parliamentary Administration (N=703) as the main source. The MPs themselves submit their curricula vitae (CVs) to the parliamentary archive. The collected CVs used to be published in book format (Giefing 1998), but can now be found as well on the Parliament's homepage under the section *Wer ist Wer*.¹ It is acknowledged that the CV's authors might seek to maximise credibility or highlight certain aspects of their professional past. This problem was remedied as much as possible through triangulation: Information was cross-checked with other reliable sources that exist for members of all state parliaments (*Landtage*), such as, for example, the biographical dictionary by Voithofer (2007) on political elites in Salzburg or the rich online database on members of the Vienna State Parliament and City Council.² In rare cases where the biographies of state legislators were more complete than information from the Parliamentary Administration, the former was treated as the primary source.

Variables

This analysis considers all political jobs occupied by an individual before winning their first *Nationalrat* mandate. What is, thus, considered is the pre-parliamentary careers path. Due to a lack of comprehensive data, all non-political jobs are omitted, such as the occupations after education or the longest formative occupation, which are known to often serve as a stepping stone to a political career (see, for example, Turner-Zwinkels, and Mills 2020).

To investigate patterns of consecutive political jobs held, general codes were assigned to the "raw information," i.e., political job positions listed in biographical entries. The coding scheme (see Table 1) is adopted from Ohmura et al. (2018) with minor adjustments in order to take into account necessary national idiosyncrasies. The scheme captures political job positions along two dimensions: First, positions are categorised according to the different levels of the Austrian federal state (local, Land,

¹ <https://www.parlament.gv.at/WWER/>, <assessed on: 26 January 2023>

² <https://www.wien.gv.at/infodat/sukri>, <assessed on: 26 January 2023>

national, EU). Second, a distinction is made between representative positions (posts that require election) and nonrepresentative positions, party positions, and government positions. It is important to note that positions in the party's women organisation were coded as party positions (at different geographical levels), which appears justified as these organisations in Austria are not separate from party membership (as is the case of Finland, for example). In a similar vein, positions (at different geographical levels) within the ÖVP's three main Leagues (Farmers' League, Business League, Workers' and Employees' League) were considered as party positions despite the fact that Leagues are not only the constituent units of the ÖVP as an "indirect party" (Müller and Steininger 1994, 2) but also independent associations (*Vereine*). This coding strategy is required as leading members of the three main Leagues are *de facto* always members in the respective local, Land or national ÖVP organisation.

In the case of jobs within parties' youth organisations, Chambers, and labour unions, different geographical levels are neglected as a fine-grained classification leads to an unmanageable number of career positions. It is important to note that the Chamber of Labour, the Business Chamber, and the Chamber of Agriculture as well as the Austrian federation of industry union (ÖGB) are the backbone of the Austrian "social partnership," which is essentially an institutionalised network of cooperation between employers and employees (Tálos 2019). Up until recently, there has been a close dovetailing between the longstanding government parties SPÖ and ÖVP, on the one hand, and chambers and labour unions, on the other.

Pre-parliamentary careers in Austria, as elsewhere, are marked not only through successions of career positions but also through the accumulation of offices—a career strategy through which politicians aim to reduce the job insecurity inherent in political careers (Borchert and Stolz 2003). However, not all political positions are marked by equal social prestige, which allows us to include hierarchy into the coding scheme. Following closely Ohmura et al. (2018, 7), I decided to apply a "hierarchy in which higher regional levels trump lower ones and in which publicly elected offices trump party positions since a smaller group of people elects candidates in party positions". Further, the hierarchical ordering of job positions also considers that job properties such as income, power, public visibility, policy influence, and opportunities for further career advancement differ between jobs. To give an example: A federal minister (code 12) certainly has more income and influence than a member

of the *Bundesrat* (code 11). It is, in contrast, difficult to establish whether the president of the Trade Union of Public Administration (code 7) with its 250,000 members nationwide is more influential than the president of Vienna's Chamber of Labour (code 6). A double function of that nature, holding a leadership position in a trade union and a Chamber does not, however, appear in the dataset. Similarly, leading labour representatives (code 6 and 7) are, in most cases, not found in state legislatures (code 8) or state governments, as their professional careers develop outside of political parties. These codes thus could have limitations, however what I found was that these are irrelevant in practise.

Table 1. Order of Analysed Career Spells.

Code	Career position	Example
0	No information available	
1	Youth party position (all levels)	State Chairman of the Young Generation
2	(Women) Party position: local level	Deputy Chairman of the party's district organisation Deputy Chairwomen of the party's district Women's Organisation
3	Legislative public position: local level	Local Council Member
4	Executive public position: local level	Major
5	(Women) Party position: Land level	State Party Chairman Chairwomen of the state Women's Organisation
6	Chamber (all levels)	President of the Upper Austria Chamber of Labour
7	Trade Union (all levels)	President of the Austrian Trade Union Federation
8	Legislative public position: Land level	Member of the State Parliament
9	Executive public position: Land level	Regional Minister
10	(Women) Party position: national level	Party Chairman Chairwomen of the Women's Organisation
11	Legislative public position: national	Member of the <i>Bundesrat</i>
12	Executive public position: national level	Federal Minister
13	Legislative position: EU level	Member of the European Parliament
14	After entry into parliament	

To comprehensively reconstruct legislative careers, I considered all years between the MP's age range of 18 and 70. Each year of a MP's activity in (party) politics corresponds to one of the 14 "career stages" listed in Table 1. The career of a MP thus consists of a succession of stages and each MP can be identified by a more or less distinct, sequence of career stages.

Analytical Strategies

The pre-parliamentary careers were analysed using sequence analysis (SA). This technique was introduced to the social sciences by Abbott and Forrest (1986) that allows us to study patterns in longitudinal data holistically, as it takes into due consideration that it is not only the number, type and order of “stages” within sequences that makes career trajectories unique but also their specific durations. Sequence comparison is core for SA (Blanchard, Bühlmann, and Gauthier 2014, 21ff.) and cluster analysis is used to create a typology of trajectories. In conjunction, both techniques allow us to identify the most “trodden trails,” i.e., sets of typical careers that help to categorise most of the actual careers studied by ignoring a multitude of smaller differences that exist even between very similar sequences.

Several different techniques can be used to identify types of careers. Here the optimal matching (OM) algorithm was applied, as it calculates the minimal sum of the cost of all arithmetic operations required to turn one sequence into another. The best way to set these costs has been a contentious issue for SA in the social sciences (Hanly, Clarke, and Steele 2016). I decided to derive costs from the estimated state frequencies. These costs were estimated using the TraMiner package in R (Gabadinho et al. 2011).

The algorithm applied compares sequences by pairs and associates a dissimilarity index to each pair (Abbott and Tsay 2000). To cluster based on dissimilarities (or distances), the Ward’s method was used. The Ward method groups careers in such a way that careers within each cluster are as homogenous as possible, i.e., within-cluster variance is minimised. A convenient way to visually represent the grouping process is the dendrogram of Ward’s hierarchical ascending clustering procedure (Ward 1963). The clustering of the remaining 703 career sequences yielded an optimal seven-cluster solution (see Figure 2), which means that altogether seven distinct types of pre-parliamentary careers were identified.

Figure 2. Dendrogram of the Ward's (1963) agglomerative procedure.

Notes. If you see clusters merged at height x , it means that the distance between these clusters was x .

Findings

Identifying the Career Pathways to the Nationalrat

Using sequence cluster analysis, I could identify seven pre-parliamentary careers that are distinct with regard to their main career stages and the timing of careers (see Table 1). Figure 3 shows the sequence plots and Table 1 summarizes the key characteristics of each career cluster.

Party Animals (32.6%). This cluster consists of 229 politicians who entered politics early in their lives, mostly between the age of 18 and 30, and became members of the *Nationalrat*, on average, at age 35. Many were active in the diverse youth party organisations and have strong roots in state as well as in local party organisations. Some have represented political parties as well in local legislatures (but not in local executives as mayors) and most have progressed through state legislatures or state party organisations into the national parliament. Besides an early career start, the key distinguishing feature is comparatively short career periods in positions at the local and state level, which suggests that individuals in this cluster have steadily climbed the party ladder.

Late Bloomers (25.9%). The most distinctive characteristic of this second largest cluster consisting of 229 politicians is that many included MPs have worked in the big chambers for business, labour, or agriculture that have served as a springboard for their political careers. Another key feature is the comparatively late start of their careers in politics, which provides these Late Bloomers with sufficient time to establish a professional career outside of politics. The average age at their initial entry into the *Nationalrat* is 46. Their political careers are diverse, but clearly, they serve for longer periods not only in Chambers but as well in local legislatures. Further, many have worked for state party organisation before winning national office. A characteristic shared with the first cluster is that Late Bloomers tend to embark on the laborious career through the party machine (dubbed *Ochsentour* in German) rather than work, for example, for local parties only. What differentiates Late Bloomers from Party Animals is the dominant profession as most cluster members come from professions (other than law) and cannot be categorised as career politicians.

Mayors (16.1%). The third cluster consists of experienced mayors and, to a far lesser extent, of heads of municipality executive bodies (*Gemeindevorstände*). Politicians grouped in this third cluster

are locally oriented in terms of future ambition, which manifests itself, inter alia, in the number of working years spent as mayors (7 on average).

Figure 3. Sequence Plots of the Political Pathways to the Austrian Parliament.

Land Legislators (8.7%). This fourth cluster describes MPs with extensive careers in the Land-level parliaments. Due to the frequently made observation that MPs at the subnational level often choose to remain in their position rather than strive for office at the national level, this group is comparatively small.

Party Localists (7.4%). Their sequence image is dominated with red colour-coding, indicating that MPs within this cluster have positions in local legislatures for a significant amount of time before being elected to the Austrian parliament. They mostly lack experience in the state or national party organisations.

Career Changers (6.7%). These individuals with no or only very short pre-parliamentary political careers enter parliament in their fifties and sixties. Besides expert outsiders such as university professors, we find athletes and journalists as well in this cluster.

Trade Unionists (2.7%). The primary characteristic of this cluster is that individuals have a board position in labour unions before entering parliament. Their careers develop mostly outside of party politics.

The juxtaposition of all seven career paths shows that the classification grid suggested by Borchert and Stolz (2011) can be applied to the Austrian case. While the pre-parliamentary careers of Early Career Starters and Late Career Starters are overwhelmingly ‘unidirectional’ as individuals tend to move from the lowest (e.g., member of the youth party) to one of highest rungs of the political ladder. In the case of Mayors, Land legislators, and Party Localists one can speak of ‘integrated’ careers that are first and foremost marked by a level hopping between local and Land politics and national politics.

Besides the fact that Career Changers tend to be predominantly male it is striking to see that two of the three ‘integrated’ career pathways are especially inaccessible to women (see Table 1). A closer examination is needed to understand to what extent these findings apply to all parties investigated.

Table 1. Description of Political Career Pathways to the *Nationalrat* (1996-2019).

	% of Population	Key Distinguishing Feature	Main Career State (except “after entry” and “none”)	Avg. Time in Main Career State	Most Occurring Career Stages in Sequence	Avg. Work-Years Political Experience [min, max]	Age at First Entry (sd)	% of Women	Education (ISCED 1-5 ISCED 6-7 ISCED 8) in %	Dominant Occupation (in %)
<i>All Politicians</i>	100% (703)	–	Legisl. local	2.3 years	Legisl. local Exec. local Legisl. state Party state	10.9 [1,42]	43.4 (8.8)	32.4%	52.8% 25.9% 21.4%	public sector jobs (16.0%)
<i>Party Animals</i>	32.6% (229)	Political Careers start early in life and often within the party youth	Party state	1.8 years	Party state Party local Party youth	9.5 [1,32]	35.5 (6.3)	33.6%	45.9% 34.1% 10.1%	career politician (29.3%)
<i>Late Bloomers</i>	25.9% (182)	Political Careers in Chambers	Chamber	1.2 years	Chamber Legisl. local Party state Party local	6.6 [1,26]	46.0 (6.0)	48.4%	51.1% 23.1% 25.8%	professions other than law (15.9%)
<i>Mayors</i>	16.1% (113)	Experience mayors	Exec. local	7 years	Exec. local Party state	12.0 [2,29]	45.1 (6.3)	19.5%	70.8% 16.8% 12.4%	public sector jobs (21.3%)
<i>Land Legislators</i>	8.7% (61)	Extensive careers in Land-level parliaments	Legisl. local	8.6 years	Legisl. state Legisl. local Exec. local	16.7 [4,38]	50.0 (5.8)	31.1%	55.7% 26.2% 18.0%	professions other than law (18.0%) teachers & professors (18.0%)
<i>Party Localists</i>	7.4% (52)	Extensive careers in local politics	Legisl. local	12.5 years	Legisl. local Exec. local Party local	17.2 [10,35]	45.7 (6.9)	17.3%	63.5% 28.9% 7.7%	professions other than law (19.2%) public sector jobs (19.2%)
<i>Career Changers</i>	6.7% (47)	No or very short Pre-parliamentary career	Legisl. local	n.a	n.a	4.7 [1,13]	56.1 (4.7)	19.1%	23.4% 21.3% 55.3%	managers & businessmen (17.0%)
<i>Trade Unionists</i>	2.7% (19)	No party career	Trade union	14.9 years	Trade union Legisl. state	19.0 [9,42]	47.3 (6.4)	21.0%	79.0% 10.5% 10.5%	public sector jobs (63.2%)

Gendered Careers and Political Parties

As it transpires from Table 2, the vast majority of elected officials come through seven pathways that are marked by a gender skew (see Table 2). One can observe that the classical political careers starting early in life and lasting for longer periods of time are more conducive to men entering office while women overwhelmingly embark on this time-intensive career path later in life, most likely after their family obligations have decreased (Ohmura et al. 2018). What is, however, far more striking, is the dominance of men in local pathways to legislative office. MPs embarking on these career routes are not only well informed about local preferences but also very likely enjoy substantial local support and name recognition among local constituencies (Binderkrantz et al. 2020). An independent test is necessary to reliably determine whether there is a (statistically) significant relationship between gender and career types. I will adopt here a traditional approach using the Pearson Chi-Square test that measures the extent to which the observed data depart from the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between the two variables, gender and career type.

The test turns out to be statistically significant not only in the case of the full sample but as well for three subsamples, namely all three large parties in terms of members (ÖVP, SPÖ) or votes (FPÖ). A proper interpretation of these results requires contextualisation. It is well established in the literature that what distinguishes the three large parties from all smaller ones (e.g., Greens, NEOS, BZÖ) is that party leaders approach the issue of candidate selection from a bottom-up perspective. This means that the order of the seat allocation process is followed and candidate lists are manufactured by proceeding from the regional to the national level (Jenny 2018). In contrast, the ranking of candidates on the national list takes centre stage in small parties while candidate lists for regional districts, for example, are clearly of secondary importance to them, which can be explained by the fact that small parties tend to win (almost) no seats on lower lists.

Residuals, i.e., differences between the observed and expected values for a given cell, were inspected to determine which specific cells make the greatest contribution to the Chi-Square (see Figure S1 in the Supplementary Material). According to Agresti (2019), standardised residuals having absolute values of about 2 indicate a lack of fit with the null hypothesis when there are a few number of cells as in Table 2. Residual analysis suggests that it is first and foremost the male dominance in clusters that

are characterised by local career pathways ('Mayors', 'Party Localists') that causes the genderedness of pre-parliamentary career paths in Austria.

Table 2. Gendered Political Career Pathways to the *Nationalrat* (absolute numbers).

	All*			ÖVP			SPÖ			FPÖ			Greens			NEOS			BZÖ		
	W	M	GR	W	M	GR	W	M	GR	W	M	GR	W	M	GR	W	M	GR	W	M	GR
Party Animals	77	152	2.0	18	49	2.7	26	35	1.3	11	47	4.3	16	8	0.5	1	4	4.0	0	8	n.a
Late Bloomers	88	94	1.14	31	29	0.9	25	23	0.9	18	32	1.8	6	3	0.5	5	3	0.6	0	2	n.a
Mayors	22	91	4.1	7	31	4.4	10	32	3.2	4	24	6.0	1	2	2.0	0	0	n.a	0	1	n.a
Land Legislators	19	42	2.2	3	14	4.7	7	12	1.7	3	12	4.0	3	1	0.3	0	0	n.a	1	3	3.0
Party Localists	9	43	4.81	3	21	7.0	5	10	2.0	0	9	n.a.	0	0	n.a.	0	1	n.a	1	1	1.0
Career Changers	9	38	4.2	3	8	2.7	1	3	3.0	3	13	4.3	1	4	4	0	2	n.a	0	1	n.a
Trade Unionists	4	15	3.8	0	2	n.a	4	13	3.3	0	0	n.a.	0	0	n.a.	0	0	n.a	0	0	n.a
Total	228	475	2.1	65	154	2.4	78	128	1.6	39	137	3.5	27	18	0.7	6	10	1.7	2	16	8.0
Chi-Square	40.243			21.907																	
df	6			6																	
Sig. level	<i>p</i> < 0.01			<i>p</i> < 0.01			<i>p</i> < 0.1*			<i>p</i> < 0.1*			<i>ns</i> *			<i>ns</i> *			<i>ns</i> *		

*MPs of the small parties Team Stronach and PILZ are included as well.

**Fisher's Exact Test conducted due to the small subsample size.

Note. The equation for calculation the gender ratio (GR) is $\frac{Men(M)}{Women(W)}$.

Discussion

This article contributes to the previous academic literature by making sense of the paradox of the persisting underrepresentation of women in national parliaments. Its key finding complements rather than challenges most other explanations, which range from gendered interests and ambition (Fox and Lawless 2014) to gendered pipelines (Thomsen and King 2020). This paper has highlighted the importance of different political arenas in multi-level politics. In a federal country like Austria, organised political system, local (and regional) pathways account for a significant proportion of all pathways to national legislative office. Furthermore, the gender gap among national legislators is likely to be impacted by women's underrepresentation in politics at lower territorial levels. With regard to regional politics, such a "bottom up effect" was found to be negligible in the Austrian case (however, see Gushchina and Kaiser 2021).

Ultimately, supply-side barriers are critical to understanding the gendered skew of local pathways to the *Nationalrat*. Given Austria's multi-level governance, the availability of political offices at the local level is extremely high. Below the nine states (*Länder*) are more than 2,000 towns, cities, and municipalities with councillors and one mayor each. However, studies carried out in 2003 showed that the percentage of female mayors was under 2%; in 1998 the figure was even as low as 1.4% (ODIHR 2014). According to official information from the Austrian Association of Town and Cities, the share of women in municipal councils (*Gemeinderäte*) hovers around 25%. Thus, in the available pool of possible candidates rooted in local politics who can decide to put themselves forward for election to the national parliament, women candidates can hardly be found.

As shown by previous in-depth research, a 'demand-side barrier' to the inclusion of women on regional constituency party lists matter as well. While the gender quota-fulfilment at the national and Land level is, in general, high as gatekeepers at higher levels are committed to gender parity principles, party elites have little control over the many regional lists that often reflect compromises between players in multiple party districts that fail to consider candidates' gender. Moreover, men are often placed as front-runners of regional district lists organised by zipper rules, i.e., male and female candidates alternate on the list (man-woman-man-women, etc.), which disadvantages women especially in small districts with only one or three seats available (Ahrens et al. 2020; Steininger 2000). This

article's finding of gendered local pathways within larger parties with bottom-up candidate selection procedures is additional evidence for party quotas being only lukewarmly embraced by local politicians.

On a more general level, this article provides further evidence that the state architecture impacts women's political opportunities and representation (Hausman, Sawyer, and Vickers 2010). One fruitful avenue for future research is to complement the structural analysis of gendered career patterns with more in-depth investigations that can reveal why exactly women are excluded more from politics at the local (or regional) level rather than the national level. Available qualitative cases studies suggest that (party-specific) discriminatory practices are not limited to the time prior to elections and operate differently at every stage of a women's political career (Drechselová 2020). Far less is known, however, about which micro-factors operate in local politics against women.

Another is to identify strategies to improve the level of women's representation in local political decision-making, thus enabling women to move up the recruitment ladder. Recent case studies have found that a larger pool of female candidates alone does not necessarily result in a higher presence of women in local councils (Maškarinec 2022). However, female mayors have shown to succeed in paving the way for more female local council members (Baskaran and Hessami 2018), thus highlighting the importance of female involvement in local politics. More research is needed to validate the generalisability of these findings.

References

- Abbott, Andrew, and John Forrest. 1986. "Optimal Matching Methods for Historical Sequences." *The Journal of Interdisciplinary History* 16(3): 471–94.
- Abbott, Andrew, and Angela Tsay. 2000. "Sequence Analysis and Optimal Matching Methods in Sociology: Review and Prospect." *Sociological Methods & Research* 29(1): 3–33.
- Agresti, Alan. 2019. *An Introduction to Categorical Data Analysis*. Third edition. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.
- Ahrens, Petra, Katja Chmielewski, Sabine Lang, and Birgit Sauer. 2020. *Gender Equality in Politics: Implementing Party Quotas in Germany and Austria*. Cham: Springer.
- Ashe, Jeanette. 2020. *Political Candidate Selection: Who Wins, Who Loses, and under-Representation in the UK*. First Edition. London; New York: Routledge.
- Ashe, Jeanette, and Kennedy Stewart. 2012. "Legislative Recruitment: Using Diagnostic Testing to Explain Underrepresentation." *Party Politics* 18(5): 687–707.
- Baskaran, Thushyanthan, and Zohal Hessami. 2018. "Does the Election of a Female Leader Clear the Way for More Women in Politics?" *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy* 10(3): 95–121.
- Binderkrantz, Anne S., Marie K. Nielsen, Helene H. Pedersen, and Mathias W. Tromborg. 2020. "Pre-Parliamentary Party Career and Political Representation." *West European Politics* 43(6): 1315–38.
- Blanchard, Philippe, Felix Bühlmann, and Jacques-Antoine Gauthier, eds. 2014. *Advances in Sequence Analysis: Theory, Method, Applications*. New York: Springer.
- Borchert, Jens. 2011. "Individual Ambition and Institutional Opportunity: A Conceptual Approach to Political Careers in Multi-Level Systems." *Regional & Federal Studies* 21(2): 117–40.
- Borchert, Jens, and Klaus Stolz. 2003. "Fighting Insecurity: Political Careers and Career Politics in the Federal Republic of Germany." *Politische Vierteljahresschrift* 44(2): 148–73.
- . 2011. "Institutional Order and Career Patterns: Some Comparative Considerations." *Regional & Federal Studies* 21(2): 271–82.
- Cowell-Meyers, Kimberly, and Laura Langbein. 2009. "Linking Women's Descriptive and Substantive Representation in the United States." *Politics & Gender* 5(4): 491–518.
- Drechselová, Lucie. 2020. *Local Power and Female Political Pathways in Turkey: Cycles of Exclusion*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Eder, Nikolaus, Marcelo Jenny, and Wolfgang C. Müller. 2015. "Winning over Voters or Fighting Party Comrades? Personalized Constituency Campaigning in Austria." *Electoral Studies* 39: 316–28.
- Edinger, Michael, and Stefan Jahr, eds. 2015. *Political Careers in Europe: Career Patterns in Multi-Level Systems*. 1. Edition. Baden-Baden: Nomos.
- EIGE. 2022. *Gender Equality Index 2022: The COVID 19 Pandemic and Care*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2839/95475> (January

- 17, 2023).
- Fiers, Stefan, and Ineke Secker. 2007. "A Career through the Party: The Recruitment of Party Politicians in Parliament." In *Democratic Representation in Europe: Diversity, Change, and Convergence*, eds. Maurizio Cotta and Heinrich Best. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 136–59.
- Fox, Richard L., and Jennifer L. Lawless. 2004. "Entering the Arena? Gender and the Decision to Run for Office." *American Journal of Political Science* 48(2): 264–80.
- . 2014. "Uncovering the Origins of the Gender Gap in Political Ambition." *American Political Science Review* 108(3): 499–519.
- Gabadinho, Alexis, Gilbert Ritschard, Nicolas S. Müller, and Matthias Studer. 2011. "Analyzing and Visualizing State Sequences in R with TraMineR." *Journal of Statistical Software* 40(4): 1–37.
- Geisberger, Tamara. 2010. "Repräsentation und Partizipation von Frauen in Politik und Wirtschaft." In *Bericht über die Situation der Frauen in Österreich*, ed. Bundesministerium für Frauen und Öffentlichen Dienst. Wien: Bundeskanzleramt, 351–86.
- Giefing, Martha, ed. 1998. *Biographisches Handbuch der österreichischen Parlamentarier, 1918-1998*. Vienna: Parlamentsdirektion.
- Gushchina, Kristina, and André Kaiser. 2021. "Multilevel Governance and Women's Legislative Representation." *European Journal of Political Research* 60(4): 934–53.
- Hanly, Mark, Paul Clarke, and Fiona Steele. 2016. "Sequence Analysis of Call Record Data: Exploring the Role of Different Cost Settings." *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series C (Applied Statistics)* 179(3): 793–808.
- Harfst, Philipp, Damien Bol, and Jean-François Laslier. 2021. "Designing Preference Voting." *Electoral Studies* 69: 102262.
- Hausman, Melissa, Marian Sawer, and Jill Vickers, eds. 2010. *Federalism, Feminism and Multilevel Governance*. Farnham: Ashgate.
- Höhmman, Daniel. 2020. "When Do Men Represent Women's Interests in Parliament? How the Presence of Women in Parliament Affects the Legislative Behavior of Male Politicians." *Swiss Political Science Review* 26(1): 31–50.
- Jenny, Marcelo. 2018. "Austria. Tradition and Innovation in Legislative Candidate Selection." In *The Selection of Politicians in Times of Crisis*, Routledge research on social and political elites, eds. Xavier Coller, Guillermo Cordero, and Antonio M. Jaime Castillo. London ; New York: Routledge, 31–48.
- Maškarinec, Pavel. 2022. "Women and Local Politics: Determinants of Women's Emergence and Success in Elections to Czech Town Councils, 1998–2018." *Urban Affairs Review* 58(2): 356–87.
- Müller, Wolfgang C. et al. 2001. *Die österreichischen Abgeordneten: Individuelle Präferenzen und politisches Verhalten*. Wien: WUV.
- . 2005. "Austria: A Complex Electoral System with Subtle Effects." In *The Politics of Electoral*

- Systems*, eds. Michael Gallagher and Paul Mitchell. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 397–416.
- Müller, Wolfgang C., and Barbara Steininger. 1994. “Party Organisation and Party Competitiveness: The Case of the Austrian People’s Party, 1945-1992.” *European Journal of Political Research* 26(1): 1–29.
- Norris, Pippa, and Joni Lovenduski. 1995. *Political Recruitment: Gender, Race, and Class in the British Parliament*. Cambridge; New York: Cambridge University Press.
- ODIHR. 2014. *Women’s Political Participation on the Local Level in Austria*. Warsaw: OSCE. <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/4/5/145551.pdf>.
- Ohmura, Tamaki, Stefanie Bailer, Peter Meißner, and Peter Selb. 2018. “Party Animals, Career Changers and Other Pathways into Parliament.” *West European Politics* 41(1): 169–95.
- Phillips, Anne. 1998. “Democracy and Representation: Or, Why Should It Matter Who Our Representatives Are?” In *Feminism and Politics*, ed. Anne Phillips. Oxford ; New York: Oxford University Press, 224–40.
- Pitkin, Hanna F. 1972. *The Concept of Representation*. Berkeley, Calif.: University of California Press.
- Rawls, John. 1999. *A Theory of Justice*. Cambridge, Mass: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.
- Sanbonmatsu, Kira. 2006. *Where Women Run: Gender and Party in the American States*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Schwindt-Bayer, Leslie A. 2011. “Women Who Win: Social Backgrounds, Paths to Power, and Political Ambition in Latin American Legislatures.” *Politics & Gender* 7(01): 1–33.
- Steininger, Barbara. 2000. “Representation of Women in the Austrian Political System 1945-1998: From a Token Female Politician Towards an Equal Ratio?” *Women & Politics* 21(2): 81–106.
- Stolz, Klaus. 2003. “Moving up, Moving down: Political Careers across Territorial Levels: Political Careers Across Territorial Levels.” *European Journal of Political Research* 42(2): 223–48.
- Tálos, Emmerich. 2019. *Sozialpartnerschaft: Ein zentraler politischer Gestaltungsfaktor der Zweiten Republik am Ende?* Innsbruck: StudienVerlag.
- Thomsen, Danielle M., and Aaron S. King. 2020. “Women’s Representation and the Gendered Pipeline to Power.” *American Political Science Review* 114(4): 989–1000.
- Turner-Zwinkels, Tomas, and Melinda C. Mills. 2020. “Pathways to Power: The Role of Preparliamentary Careers and Political Human Capital in the Obtainment of Cabinet Positions.” *Legislative Studies Quarterly* 45(2): 207–52.
- Voithofer, Richard. 2007. *Politische Eliten in Salzburg: Ein biografisches Handbuch 1918 Bis Zur Gegenwart*. Wien: Böhlau.
- Ward, Joe H. 1963. “Hierarchical Grouping to Optimize an Objective Function.” *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 58: 236–44.
- Wilensky, Harold L. 1961. “Orderly Careers and Social Participation: The Impact of Work History on Social Integration in the Middle Mass.” *American Sociological Review* 26(4): 521–39.

Supplementary Material

Figure S1. Residual Heat Map

Notes. The colour represents the level of the residual for each cell in the contingency table. More specifically, red means that there are more observations in that cell than would be expected under the null model of independence. Blue means that there are fewer observations than would have been expected.